

Snakemake's SLURM Executor Plugin - improved Support for GPUs

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Snakemake's SLURM Executor Plugin - improved Support for GPUs

1.1 Authors

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2 Description

This work was completed as part of the Snakemake Hackathon 2025.

2.0.1 Problem

Previously, using GPUs or other special resources using Snakemake's SLURM executor plugin required using the `slurm_extra` resource. A catch-all parameter, which required nested quoting:

```
resource:  
    slurm_extra="'gres=gpu:1'"
```

This was cumbersome and error-prone as users were required to account for the nested quoting in their configuration files, too.

2.0.2 Solution

This release updates the Snakemake executor plugin for SLURM batch system used on HPC systems. It adds support for immediate GPU resource requests and improved SLURM account handling. Building on the existing plugin, these enhancements significantly simplify workflow submission for workflows using GPU resources (e.g. artificial intelligence or molecular dynamics simulations).

2.0.3 Key Features

- **GPU Acceleration:** The plugin simplifies GPU resource requests within Snakemake, enabling users to leverage GPU acceleration without complex SLURM quoting. The plugin translates Snakemake's GPU requests into appropriate SLURM `--gres` or `--gpus` flags.
- **Flexible SLURM Account Management:** The plugin automatically detects and applies your SLURM account. For clusters without account permissions, the account specification can be disabled, ensuring broad compatibility.
- **Robust Account Detection (v1.0.1):** Improved logic for detecting and validating SLURM accounts, addressing previous issues with unreliable environment variable parsing.

Now, the executor offers to distinguish between simple GPU requests, e.g.

```
resource:
  gpu=2
```

Requests 2 GPUs for the current workflow step.

Alternatively, specify a GPU model, too:

```
resource:
  gpu=2,
  gpu_model="a100"
```

Requests 2 'a100' GPUs for the current workflow step.

You can utilize the `--gres` flag for advanced configurations, too (this was in use for SLURM, prior to the introduction of the `--gpus` flag):

```
resource:
  gres="gpu:a100:2"
```

Analogous to SLURM, users may request CPUs per reserved GPU

```
resource:
  gpu=2,
  cpus_per_gpu=4
```

2.1 Notes

- To be consistent within Snakemake, the executor uses a `gpu` resource, not `gpus`.
- As some HPC sides disallow reserving CPU in GPU partitions at all, a setting of `cpus_per_gpu` to values of zero or less, no `--cpus-per-gpu` or `--cpus-per-task` flag is issued upon job submission.
- This work supersedes a [previous version](#) which was used for testing the publication process with Research Equals.

2.2 References

- [version 1.0.0](#) Version 1.0.0 contains a bugfix for `logdir` misconstrues when wildcards with a leading slash are used, see [this PR for reference](#).
- [version 1.0.1](#)

2.3 Acknowledgement

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